

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Platform v1

WP3_D3.2

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1 Introduction

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016c, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform (Durán-Escudero, García-Peñalvo, & Therón-Sánchez, 2017; García-Peñalvo, 2016b; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017), which represents a technological ecosystem for the project development (García-Holgado & García-Peñalvo, 2013, 2016; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & García-Holgado, 2017).

This deliverable presents summary of the status of the WYRED platform, where can be found all information about the architecture of this platform, the used technologies and the current functionalities.

2 Technical report

In this section is described all platform information from the point of view of a developer.

2.1 Platform's architecture

The platform architecture has an important role in this project due to it is not a monolithic software because it has been created joining and adapting other developments. The main software used is Drupal a CMS (Content Management System), that it is the base for the platform. To achieve all WYRED requirements it has been installed some Drupal modules and it also has been developed some specific modules and the WYRED's theme.

At the moment, the platform uses two servers (Figure 1):

- A server with Drupal and its dependencies (LAMP).
- A server with Apereo CAS, MySQL and the WYRED API.

Figure 1. WYRED platform deployment information

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2.2 Platform technologies

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Software	Type	Server	Use	Technologies
Drupal	CMS	A	WYRED's platform	PHP, HTML, CSS, LESS, JS, Drupal, Grunt
Apereo CAS	CAS	B	Single sign-on Manage users' private information	JAVA, Spring, SQL
MySQL	Database	B	Keep users' private information and inclusion data private	SQL
WYRED's API	REST API	B	Access all information saved in the Database	PHP, Slim, SQL

Other technologies and skills have been also required:

- Git as version control system. It's linked with Redmine a project management tool.
- A large knowledge in systems administration: scripts, LAMP, Docker, Let's encrypt...

3 Results

The following section describes the main parts of the WYRED platform with detailed captures of each view.

3.1 Registration

WYRED is a private community, for this reason in order to register, you have to get a personal invitation (Figure 2).

The screenshot shows a web form for sending a personal invitation. At the top, there are four tabs: 'Accepted', 'Pending', 'Expired', and 'Invite by e-mail' (which is highlighted in orange). Below the tabs are several input fields: 'E-mail *', 'Name *', 'Surname *', and 'Date of birth *'. The 'Date of birth *' field has a date picker showing '11/09/2017'. Below these fields is a 'Community' dropdown menu with a refresh icon. At the bottom left, there is a 'Send invitation' button.

Figure 2. Personal invitation

With the invitation, a user can access to the registration page, where she will have to fill some fields to create his public and private profile and to configure how he wants to use the platform (Figure 3).

The registration page is a vertical form with a blue background. It contains the following sections and fields:

- Registration:** Fields for "E-mail address" (containing "asdasdasdasdasdas@sympatico.com"), "Password", and "Confirm password".
- Public data:** A section titled "Public data" with a sub-note: "These data will be visible for all users and they will help you to engage in the platform". It includes a "Language" dropdown menu with options: English, Danish, Spanish, Turkish, Italian, and Other. Below it is a "Topics of Interest" section with a list of 15 topics, each with a radio button: Self-image, self-confidence; Tolerance to different cultures/opinions; Reliability of information on the internet and social media; Mental wellbeing; Employment prospects; Cyber-bullying, shaming; Necessary changes in education; Internet safety and privacy; Border stereotypes / discrimination; Causes of stress among young people; Roles of parents, friends and peer groups; Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and in the society; Environmental problems; Adults' misunderstanding of young people; and Crime.
- Private data:** A section titled "Private data" with a sub-note: "These data will keep hidden in the platform and only the administrator will be able to consult them". It includes fields for "Name", "Surname", "Country" (a dropdown menu with "Select a value"), "Gender" (radio buttons for Male and Female), "Education level" (a dropdown menu with "Select a value"), and "Year of Birth".
- Language settings:** A section titled "Language settings" with a "Language" dropdown menu showing "Spanish (Español)" selected and "English" as an option.
- Picture:** A section titled "Picture" with a "Select an avatar" label and four avatar icons: a woman with dark hair, a woman with white hair, a man with glasses, and a woman with blonde hair.

Figure 3. Registration page

3.2 First steps

When a user is correctly registered, she will see a welcome message (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Welcome page

Then she should visit the help page in order to learn a bit about the platform and how to solve some common problems (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Help page

The user can also see the available communities in the page for the communities (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Communities page

Finally, the user should check if there are any events soon (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Events page

3.3 Take part of a community

The user can subscribe to all communities that he is interested in order to take part (Figure 8).

Figure 8. A community page

Then, the user can write in the opened forum threads (Figure 9).

Figure 9. A forum thread where the user can participate

3.4 User's profile

Finally, the user has a place where he can see his own profile (Figure 10).

Figure 10. The user profile

The user also has access to the inclusion form in order to improve and study about the diversity in the WYRED context (Figure 11).

Dear participant,

In empowering children and young people to get heard in the digital society, a core aim of the WYRED project is to include a broad range of different voices, ideas and opinions into the project. We regard diverse perspectives to be a most valuable resource in dealing with (future) societal changes or digital developments. Therefore, in the following we ask you to answer some questions which focus on diversity and inclusion.

Gender

Which gender do you attribute to yourself? *

- Select -

Age

Your year of birth *

- Select -

Educational or work background

What is your highest level of education? *

- Select -

At the moment are you student in formal education? *

- Select -

If you are no student in formal education: What are you doing in the moment?

Non-formal training

Figure 1. Inclusion form

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